

A Spinning Disk Test Stand for Two-Color, Tungsten Oxide Based Optical Memory System*

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Abstract— We have constructed and tested a spin stand based demonstration system for a new form of optical memory. Based on a new two color storage process which utilizes a form of tungsten oxide as the physical medium, this system offers potential advantages in storage density, write speed, signal to noise, processing flexibility, data robustness, and overall cost. In this paper we describe the system and its performance on prototype disks. Issues regarding choices of wavelengths, write power and speed will be discussed.

gain the largest market share, and advances in storage density are continuous.

MO technology is based on materials that rotate the laser beam's polarization, by a small amount, upon reflection off the surface. TeraStor Corp. (San Jose, California) announced the most recent MO advancement, claiming a 10x increase in areal density over current magnetic and MO storage methods. Their first product will be a removable drive with 20-GBytes per surface. This storage increase is due to a combination of magnetic and magneto-optic technologies. A flying head has been developed which eliminates the need for a focus servo system, and the other key component is a solid immersion lens. This lens reduces the magnetic bit cell size so that more bits can be written on tracks that are narrower than those of magnetic or magneto-optic drives [5]. The technology's major drawback is that because there is no protective layer over the medium, dust and debris can obliterate data, especially in a removable configuration [6].

Another advancement is known as MO7, a magneto-optical system with a capacity of 7-GBytes on a 12-cm diameter disk. This format would move the MO technology away from the 3.5-inch formats. MO7 technology can be adapted to read DVD read only memory (DVD-ROM) and CD-ROM disks but the reverse is impossible which increases the market for MO7. MO7 is intended as an auxiliary storage system for personal computers providing a possible substitute for hard-disk drives, or can be used to make a full backup of hard drives. However, MO7 does not yet have the capacity to store the base requirement of 133 minutes of MPEG-2 compressed video for DVD-ROM disks [7].

An additional disadvantage of MO in general is that the signal to noise ratio (S/N) is very weak. To aid in reading the material, statistical methods such as partial response maximum likelihood (PRML) technologies need to be

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1. INTRODUCTION

Ultra-dense memory is becoming essential in order to meet the increasing demands of both the military and commercial world. Specific applications include image processing for medical video and intelligence purposes, satellite communications, airborne reconnaissance, and high speed digital libraries. The most current marketed optical memory are Magneto-Optic (MO) and Digital Versatile Disk (DVD). MO and DVD in its rewritable form are both able to directly overwrite and are capable of incorporating two layers [1], [2], [3], [4]. MO and DVD companies are competing to

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employed. In addition, MO material is expensive due to poor yield because of adhesion problems of the material. MO has a lifetime of 1-10 million cycles before the material starts to pit. Pitting occurs when the material microscopically flakes off, and the system requires the use of lookup tables to catalogue the pitted areas on the disk.

Phase change works by the process of turning an amorphous structured material to a crystalline structure which changes the reflectivity of the surface. For tellurium suboxide the amorphous state of the material is 18 % reflecting, while the crystalline state is 26 % reflecting [8]. Phase change material has a signal to noise ratio that is better than MO, but it eventually will reach a limit where the material will no longer revert to an amorphous state, but remains in a crystalline state. Rewritable DVD has several formats called DVD-RW, DVD-RAM, and DVD+RW. Unlike rewritable CDs (CD-RW) and DVD-RW [9] disks that have a lifetime on the order of one thousand cycles [10], DVD-RAM has a larger lifetime, 100,000 rewrites [9]. Part of the problem with phase change material in general is "bit creep"; that is, the material has problems with the bits "moving" due to the continuously changing phase. Rewritable DVD also relies on PRML to increase data densities and data integrity [11].

DVD-ROM can store 4.7-GBytes on a single side of a 12-cm disk and is large enough to store a 133 minute movie [12]. DVD is expected to store 17 GBytes on a 12-cm diameter disc by the turn of the century. This is achieved by having four layers all together, two layers on each disk side. Current rewritable DVD is a disappointment in the home entertainment industry because rewritable DVD does not offer enough capacity to store an entire movie. Sony Corp. developed a prototype rewritable DVD-RAM drive that with a blue-green laser with power output of 20-mW is capable of writing a 12-GByte disc [13]. They are claiming that with the onset of a 410-nm laser, capacity would increase to 18-GBytes. However, the "bit creep" problem is worse at smaller spot sizes. Capacity increase is not only related to wavelength, but also to the use of a higher numerical aperture (NA) lens of .85 and a new disk structure [13].

Currently available is DVD-R, write once media, offering 3.9-GBytes for \$30 single sided and \$45 double sided. As mentioned earlier, rewritable DVD has three competing technologies, DVD-RW, DVD+RW and DVD-RAM. DVD-RW uses 12-cm disk with a 3.9-GByte capacity and a format dictated by a consortium of Hewlett-Packard, Philips Electronics, Sony Electronics, Mitsubishi, Ricoh and Yamaha Corp. However, Sony and Philips broke from the forum recently to develop DVD+RW, which stores 3-GBytes of information [14] and has its own format. The DVD-RAM has different reflectivity and different formatting techniques [15]. DVD-RAM offers a 2.6-GByte capacity single sided or 5.2-GBytes double sided. Rewritable DVD pays the price in capacity compared to DVD-ROM due to the fact that it is rewritable. DVD+RW and DVD-RW offer the advantage over DVD-RAM not only by allowing slightly more capacity, but also by eliminating the need for a caddy and ensuring CD-R compatibility [15]. Improvements are continuous; for

example, the format developed by NEC's Technology Development Center allows 5.2-GBytes on a single side [15].

DVD-RAM is intended for the consumer, business, and graphic markets to use as an inexpensive, reliable means for archival backup [16]. DVD-R and DVD-RW are intended for those who want to write a sample disc and test it before producing a final DVD-ROM [9]. DVD-R and DVD-RW drives are expensive, costing between \$5000 and \$15,000, while DVD-RAM average \$600 [9]. Apparently, one of the main concerns of the DVD working groups is how to maintain compatibility with the next generation of DVD-RAM disks [7].

If the "bit creep" problem can be solved, nine hours of studio quality audio and video are achievable with future 17-GByte DVD-ROM capacity. DVD uses the MPEG-2 digital video encoding standard and the Dolby AC3 audio encoding standard. The digital nature of the media allows lower duplication costs of entertainment content and provides multiple language support, parental control, interactivity, and pay-per-view controlled encryption. DVD players incorporated into personal computers will not only provide additional storage capacity but enhanced training, game and entertainment capabilities [17].

Given that the technologies keep getting better, it is difficult for alternatives to break into the market and compete. However, it is possible that no one technology will dominate because each has unique properties, and the demand for storage is so enormous that each player can provide a different solution. We believe we have a new memory that is able to compete significantly and possibly supersede both technologies, with the area initially to be targeted being the archival area. The memory is based on tungsten oxide material, WO_3 , and was co-invented by Rome Laboratory and Syracuse University [18]. In this paper we first explain the theoretical science of the material, and then move to explain system parameters and results. Finally, then we provide some insight to the cost of a real system and market value.

2. THE WO_3 - W_2O_5 SYSTEM

The electrochromic and photochromic properties of the tungsten oxide system have been well known [19] for over 30 years. WO_3 is a yellow material that is slightly semiconducting and represents the lowest energy form of tungsten in contact with molecular gas phase oxygen. It exists as a monoclinic solid [20] from room temperature to approximately 300° - 400° C. A first order phase transition to an orthorhombic form occurs in this temperature range, and very little evaporation of tungsten in any form occurs below 800° - 900° C.

Exchange of oxygen both within the lattice and between the solid and surrounding gas phase is well known [21]. The surface region of the material can be manipulated so that it is either more or less oxygen deficient with respect to

stoichiometric WO_3 . Oxygen deficiency leads to W^{+5} centers and the changing of the color of the material from yellow to blue. Concurrent with the color change, electrical properties, e.g. the electrical resistance, change by orders of magnitude [22], [23].

The change in the color from yellow to blue in the WO_3 - W_2O_5 system, respectively, is indicative of a change in index of refraction. This change can be purely photochromic or electrochromic. We summarize the purely photochromic approach using the following equations to emphasize the fact that the degree of oxygen deficiency

is highly variable and that an infinite number of modifications exist. These different forms, in this case, having the general formula $\text{W}_n\text{O}_{3n-1}$, are referred to as Magnelli phases [24] and the coalescence growth [25] of these species on the surface of WO_3 form what are known as "crystallographic shear" (CS) planes.

In the photochromic context, incident light is absorbed by the medium causing the formation of mobile oxygen atoms and oxygen ion type species, which react with each other to form molecular oxygen [18]. In the process, the W^{+6} on the WO_3 is reduced to W^{+5} forming W_2O_5 , W_4O_{11} or higher order species of the form $\text{W}_n\text{O}_{3n-1}$. This molecular oxygen desorbs from the surface, thereby stabilizing the $\text{W}_n\text{O}_{3n-1}$. When the partial pressure of oxygen in the surrounding gas phase is sufficiently low, the equilibrium is shifted towards $\text{W}_n\text{O}_{3n-1}$ driven mostly by the large entropy increase due to formation of gas phase oxygen from bound oxygen.

Concurrent with the loss of oxygen, the lattice rearranges from the corner sharing WO_6 octahedra comprising the WO_3 material to rows of edge sharing octahedra comprising the $\text{W}_n\text{O}_{3n-1}$, the blue, reduced oxide. The arrangement of the octahedra determines the size and shape of the spaces, often long channels, in between the octahedra through which various species, including water, protons, and hydroxyl groups diffuse. Thus, the degree of oxygen deficiency determines the mobility of the reactants and products of the electronic and photochromic reactions.

We make use of two wavelengths to create the photochromic response. Simultaneously presented near infrared (IR), such as a Nd:YAG laser beam at 1.06- μm , and doubled YAG at 532-nm are used to write blue bits on the yellow material. The IR light offers heat to weaken the chemical bonds, while the visible green or blue light provides electronic excitation. The net effect is that the 532-nm radiation causes a fast (ps) electron transfer from an oxygen to a tungsten. When lattice oxygen is driven out, the additional electron then can move from one tungsten atom in the written spot to another. This resonant process, called "intervalence transfer", is associated with the absorption of

visible light, making the material appear dark blue in color. The color change to blue is permanent until the material is reheated to a temperature greater than 400° C either in an oven for global erase, or by a concentrated infrared laser beam for spot erase. Although we use two colors to provide the photochromic reaction, at sufficient energy levels it will occur for each wavelength alone. This is because at high enough energies, the single wavelength provides substantial heat as well as electronic excitation.

For technologically interesting surfaces, adsorbed water and oxygen must be considered as being present. According to Bianchin [23] and Yoshiike [26], the presence of a proton donor enhances the photochromic response. In addition, the electrochromic response will certainly be enhanced by the presence of electrolyte, particularly if it is present in the channels. One way of representing the reaction is given below in Equations 3, 4, and 5.

Water that is present on the surface and near surface regions of the oxide material is in equilibrium with ambient gas phase, i.e. air, and reacts under the influence of the appropriate applied potential gradient according to the following half-cell reactions. There may be other reactions as well, although these reactions have been implicated by comparison with reactions thought [27] to occur on titanium oxide surfaces within the gas column spanning a scanning tip probe and the surface. The voltages are electrochemical potentials with the usual thermodynamic implications.

These comprise the net reaction summarized by reaction 5

whereby, if mass transfer allows mutual neutralization of H^+ and OH^- , this may be more accurately depicted as equation 6. The effects of mass transfer must be important to determining the lifetime of a written spot. The negative -0.7987 V electrode potential implies that the equilibrium position of equation 6 is far to the left, i.e. a "written" blue spot does not turn yellow spontaneously by reaction with ambient water.

It also seems probable that any H_2 generated by reaction 6 and O_2 that is produced by reaction 1, as well as atmospheric oxygen, combine to reform at least some of the H_2O making the overall process reversible.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

The tungsten oxide material was fabricated at the Cornell Nanofabrication Facility. The material was dc-magnetron sputtered from a WO_3 target. Substrates were 9.5-cm aluminum discs from Cerion Corporation (Champagne,

Illinois). Films deposited were blue indicating oxygen deficiency. Typically, the darker the blue the greater the deficiency. Film thickness was determined to be approximately 150-nm using a Tencor Instruments Alpha-Step 500 profilometer.

A system was built based on an AcuTrac™ spin stand purchased from Teletrac Inc. (Santa Barbara, California). Figure 1 illustrates the optical setup, while Figure 2 shows the data acquisition and control system. A Nanolase Inc. model NG1040 diode pumped frequency doubled, 532-nm, solid state laser provided the visible beam. A Newport model 835 power meter determined that the maximum average power incident on the material was approximately .6-mW. This translates to a maximum energy/pulse of 30-nJ, or 206.59-nJ/μm² using a theoretical FWHM spot size value of .4-μm. A Spotscan model 0390 optical knife edge profiler measured the 1/e² spot size to be approximately 1-μm, and sizes of written spots on tracks were verified with a high power microscope and reticule. The Olympus focusing objective model ULWD MIRPLAN 80 used has a numerical aperture (NA) of .75, and was designed to focus visible and near IR light in the same plane.

The IR beam was provided by a SDL, Inc. model 5762-A6 1-W monolithically integrated master oscillator/ power amplifier (MOPA) laser diode that operates at 985-nm and is modulated by an acousto-optic (AO) modulator model AOM-40 from Intra-Action Corporation. Approximately

7.74-mW is the maximum amount of power incident on the material. The modulated first order IR diffracted beam was combined with a Uniphase model 216-1 HeNe laser beam at 632.8-nm. Both infrared and red beams pass through the back of mirror that is highly transmitting beyond 780-nm and highly reflecting at 488-nm. At this point all three laser beams are collinear and travel the same path through to the objective to be focused on the disk in the same plane. White light is incident to provide viewing with a Pulnix model TM-540 CCD camera. For this particular system there was no z-servo to detect focus error or mechanism to detect relative beam position. This led to amplitude variations in the data.

For the data acquisition and control of the spin stand system shown in Figure 2, the system was controlled by a Labview program. Writes and reads of a track were referenced to the Spindle Sync signal produced by the spin stand. This signal occurred once for each revolution of the spindle and represented a particular position of the spindle. When used in combination with the Trigger Circuit it gave us an absolute time and position reference for a write and subsequent reads of a particular track. Therefore, we could align acquired write and read waveforms in time and know their position on the disk.

A sequence of pulses could be written using the green, IR or both green and IR lasers. The signals were free running in that they were not synced to the disk's rotation. The green

Figure 1. Optical setup of spinstand system.

laser was only capable of producing a write signal that was its 2-ns, 20-KHz Q-switch signal (modulation). The IR laser could be modulated with a variety of pulse widths and rep rates using a Hewlett Packard pulse generator model 8130A and the AO cell already mentioned. A write with the combination of both beams was accomplished by syncing the IR to the green Q-switch signal. The green detector signal provided the Q-switching signal to trigger the pulse generator that drives the AO cell. This modulated the IR beam at the same 20-KHz as the green beam Q-switching. However, the IR pulse width could be varied with the pulse generator. Due to jitter in the green beam, the pulse width of the infrared IR beam was set for 6-us for most experiments reported in this paper, in order to ensure that the IR and green beams were overlapped in time. The detectors used to detect the green and IR beams were Thor Labs DC-350-MHz PiN diodes model det2-SI.

To write a track the desired beam(s) (IR , green or both lasers) were unblocked. Then a Labview program initiated the write sequence by sending an RS-232 signal to the trigger circuit. This circuit then waited for the Spindle Sync pulse from the Spindle Controller. When the pulse arrived, the circuit opened a Uniblitz shutter model T132 for a predetermined amount of time allowing the write beam(s) to illuminate the disk. This wrote a sequence of pulses on a certain percentage of the track. The trigger circuit also triggered a LeCroy oscilloscope model 9354AL that acquired and saved the traces to disk. Labview was capable of capturing the data from the oscilloscope allowing the file to be opened by different graphical programs.

A read was performed with a HeNe laser. The read channel was very basic consisting of a New Focus DC-125 MHz detector model 1801 and the oscilloscope. The same

Figure 2. Spindata acquisition and control.

Labview program initiated a read by sending another RS-232 signal to the trigger circuit. When this circuit received the spindle sync pulse from the Spindle Controller, it opened the shutter for a predetermined amount of time allowing the HeNe beam to illuminate the disk. The trigger circuit also triggered the oscilloscope to acquire the read signal. Again, Labview was capable of capturing the data from the oscilloscope allowing the file to be opened by different graphical programs.

4. RESULTS

When writing on the material with green light alone, the spots turn dark blue indicating that the material is moving toward W_2O_5 as shown in reaction 1. The reaction in this direction we call a "write". When the IR beam is incident alone on the material, white spots are visible indicating that the material is forced in the reverse reaction and turning toward WO_3 . This occurs with $360\text{-}\mu\text{J}/\mu\text{m}^2$, given a FWHM spot size of $.8\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ for the IR beam. The reaction in this direction we designate as an "erase". Both wavelengths incident together, however, provide a write. This supports our theory that when applied together, the IR acts as a facilitator, and the green provides electronic excitation. An erase of a written spot in this system was not provided because of insufficient IR power. The contrast ratio of the

spots is plotted against applied power for each wavelength alone and shown in Figures 4 and 5.

The contrast ratio was calculated as the measured reflected power of the HeNe beam before a spot was written divided by the reflected power of the HeNe beam after the spot was written. The small declines on the graph, for example at $450\text{-}\mu\text{W}$, can be attributed to the focus not being exactly perfect due to lack of z-servo which contributes to a variation in spot sizes leading to a change in reflected HeNe power. The important feature in Figure 4 is the general tendency of the contrast ratio to increase with more applied power. This implies that more power turns the material a darker blue.

The linear fit in Figure 5 shows the general tendency for the contrast ratio to decrease with applied power. This is because the chemical reaction is occurring in the opposite direction as Figure 4, and the film is turning from being slightly oxygen deficient to being more oxygenated. The maximum contrast ratio corresponding to a color change is not as strong as in Figure 4, but it is strong enough to be detectable. The sharp increase occurring approximately at 4.75-mW as well as the smaller variations can also be attributed to not maintaining proper focus through z-servo. The focus was manually adjusted near these outlying data points. Smaller variation can also be attributed to a variety of causes that are discussed later.

Figure 4. Contrast ratio of spots written with green light alone.

Figure 5. Contrast ratio of spots written with IR beam alone.

Figure 6. Contrast ratio of green light incident alone, IR light incident alone, and both incident together.

Figure 6 shows that the contrast ratio of both IR and green together compared to each wavelength separately at maximum power for each wavelength. The fact that at maximum incident power the contrast ratio of the green alone in this graph compared to Figure 4 is not as high can be attributed to film non-uniformity. The important fact depicted is that both beams together yield a stronger contrast than either one by themselves.

Threshold power levels for the green and IR beams were determined. An arbitrary spin speed of 200-rpm was chosen to write tracks. A power level was classified as a threshold

if it was slightly capable of writing alone. Figure 7 shows the read of a track written with a green beam having an average power threshold value of .491-mW. Figure 8 shows the read of a track written with the IR beam alone having an average power threshold value of 3.432-mW. Figure 9 shows the read beam of a third track that was written with both wavelengths incident. The magnitude of the read signal data in Figure 9 is larger compared to the read signals in Figures 7 and 8. This is important because lower powers can be used to write using the combined wavelengths rather than writing with a higher power for a single wavelength to achieve a higher contrast ratio.

Figure 7. Read of a track written at green threshold levels.

Figure 8. Read of a track written at IR threshold levels.

Figure 9. Read of a track written with green and IR combined at threshold levels.

Figure 10. Alignment of write beams with read beam in time.

Figure 10 shows the write beams are both overlapped in time and correspond to the timing of the read beam's signal. The strength of the read signal improves when bits are written using powers greater than threshold values.

We calculated S/N at various disk rpms. A disk track was written with the green laser at a disk speed of 200-rpm. Then the SNR was calculated using the read signal produced at 200, 1000, and 4000 rpm. The SNR was calculated using the formula

$$SNR(dB) = \frac{(\text{mean})^2}{\sigma_n^2} \quad (7)$$

The mean is the mean of the signal pulses in the read signal and σ_n is the standard deviation of the noise (read signal minus the signal pulses). Note that the noise includes the contributions of the media, HeNe read laser, and the read channel. The results shown below

RPM	SNR
200	24 dB
1000	25 dB
4000	22 dB

indicate that there is no significant degradation in S/N when spinning close to the state-of-the art DVD speed of 4652 rpm.

5. DISCUSSION

We demonstrated a successful new memory system. This system, however, did not provide for z-servo or any method of beam tracking. Because such a high numerical aperture objective was used, many aberrations were introduced as the disc tilted. The film uniformity was not perfect, which contributes to disk wobble and focus problems. In addition, although these films were deposited in a clean room environment, they were handled in the ambient atmosphere, and visual inspection showed that they picked up water and various forms of debris. Visual inspection also showed that bad regions were still recordable with high contrast, but the z-servo problem gave the most inconsistencies. The read detection mechanism was far away from the disc so that other surfaces such as pellicles add to vibration problems. The read beam by nature is larger in spot size compared to the written spot, which contributes to a S/N. The read laser and detector used were noisy. Yet even given these system drawbacks, a significant raw S/N of 24 dB has been achieved. The read channel had unlimited bandwidth, and

the noise included detector noise, laser noise and media noise. Much better S/N can be achieved in a second generation prototype that addresses these deficiencies.

The MPEG-2 video standard used in DVD permits a data rate up to 9.8-Mbits/sec at the output of the MPEG-2 decoder. The actual average DVD data rate is approximately .52-MBytes/sec. Audio disks play at 44,100 samples per second. At this speed CD-ROMs deliver a 1X reference data rate of 153-KBytes/sec. Typically, CD-ROM's spin faster than audio, so 2X would deliver 300-KBytes/sec. Vibration and servo problems start to occur around 10X and 12X. CD and DVD both still use constant linear velocity (CLV). This means that the rotation rate varies and is maximum at the inner diameter of 25-mm. A CD 1X rotation rate at the inner diameter is 580-rpm. The DVD 1X user data rate is 1.1-MBytes/sec, and uses a 1X CLV of 3.49-m/sec. At the inner diameter, 1X rotation speed is 4652-rpm. Hard disk drive state-of-the-art speed is at 10,000-rpm.

We were able to write on our media at 10,000 rpm with some reduced contrast. However, in our laboratory environment, we chose to test at slow speeds for safety precautions. A slightly smaller S/N was obtained when spinning at 4000-rpm compared to 200 or 1000-rpm. When spinning at high speeds additional vibrations occur and without measures taken to correct for them, a slight decrease in S/N is expected. Current optical memory obtains a 60-dB S/N with a perfect system. Though our S/N is approximately 24-dB, this was measured with a crude system, and it is expected to surpass 60-dB easily.

A single layer of DVD-ROM as mentioned earlier can store up to 4.7-GBytes. WO₃ disk technology can surpass this amount. Because tungsten oxide does not have a the large volume change that phase change has between states, "bit creep" will be much less of a problem. Typically, on a 12-cm disk, the data zone width is only 33-mm wide. This is due to the area needed for clamping, lead in, lead out, and the space for the outer rim. Using DVD track pitch width (.74- μ m), the number of rotations to read the data area is 44,594.6. The inner data zone radius is 25-mm. So a total track length can be computed to be 11,628.14-m. Our FWHM spot size is .4- μ m. If we use a conservative spacing of .6- μ m between written spots, we can achieve 11.6-GBytes on a single side. By moving spots and tracks closer together, obviously, more capacity can be achieved.

DVD can only achieve up to two layers on a single side, so 17-GBytes will be the limit. Our system offers future capability in that different transition metal oxides, e.g. MoO₃, work in the same manner as tungsten oxide [17]. Transition metal oxides are strong Raman [28], [29], [30], [31] scatters, and each oxide has a different Raman wavelength shift. The beam does not have to be focused on the layer to detect the Raman shift. Resonant cavity detectors that are narrow (4-nm) in bandwidth and made for each layer's Raman shifted signal can be used to read out all layers at once. The layers can also be made to be selective in wavelength to allow simultaneous read out with a

broadband source. Layering a surface with multiple oxides will provide more density than DVD can achieve.

Disc capacity on a single layer is related to wavelength, NA of the objective, and pit and track format. Our material is limited in capacity by these same parameters. Sony's prototype disc stores 12-GBytes but needs a laser power of 20-mW. Our material threshold energy is approximately .4-mW or less. DVD will eventually reach either a wavelength limit or require more power with lower wavelengths because heat is what causes the material to turn from amorphous to crystalline and back. Our material becomes more efficient with a decrease in wavelength as well as allowing for more density. Yoshiike [26] measured a 200-ps write speed at 337-nm. Our system has proven 2-ns write speeds at 532-nm. The sources are becoming commercially available to provide for these densities. The diode pumped doubled solid state lasers can fit in a human hand, and the powers needed in our material are small enough for vertical cavity surface emitting lasers (VCSELs) to be used for the IR source. The use of arrays for simultaneous writing will tremendously increase disk to processor I/O rates. Also, the substrates used in these experiments were aluminum. Thresholds are expected to decrease when used on glass disks because of less thermal conductivity.

Writing sources are needed for rewritable drives, but our initial goal is to use it as a write once memory (WORM) and a ROM. Our material offers great capability to replace tape used in massive archiving. The system described in this paper uses three wavelengths. In a practical rewritable situation, two wavelengths would be used to read, write and erase. Lowering the green power below the write threshold would allow for reading. Our current system reads with HeNe powers of approximately 40- μ W that is incident on the material, but do to multiple surface losses, the detector sees powers on the order of 1- μ W. This implies that the power of green lasers could potentially be lowered to these values to provide a sufficient read. A WORM and/or ROM application would not need the two lasers; a single green laser would provide the write needed in a WORM and the read by adjusting the power levels of the same laser.

Our material offers simplicity in manufacturing that will aid in decreasing costs. Rewritable CD and DVD discs have reflective layers on polycarbonate substrates and special layers are added to add protection from material flow during its molten state while it is transitioning and to control thermal time constants [12]. We demonstrated a single layer of easily deposited material that was not protected in any manner, and it still provided accurate strong read signals. Our form of memory is chemically encoded, making it resistant to errors due to dust, surface roughness, and other physical imperfections, especially if Raman techniques are incorporated into the read channel. The material is rugged enough to withstand large temperature fluctuations, often found in warehouses. The material needs to be heated to 400° C to erase, 800° C before it starts to sublime, and 1300° C before it disassociates. Our material is polarization independent which can aid in lowering manufacturing costs because polarizing optics are slightly more expensive. The objective in our system may initially be expensive because it

will have to be specially designed to focus the visible and IR write wavelengths in the same plane, but once it is mass produced its cost will decrease.

Because the signal to noise ratio is so strong, the bits can be placed closer together and the use of PRML tactics may not have to be incorporated into a drive to ensure data integrity. Eliminating these statistical methods could also contribute to a possible decrease in drive costs.

6. CONCLUSION

We have demonstrated a new type of optical memory that is directly comparable to state-of-the-art optical memory. Using two wavelengths, Ir and visible, allows lowering writing power requirements of our media. Our memory offers advantages that include stronger signal to noise ratio, lower power requirements, and easier manufacturing capability. Our memory provides a means of having multiple layers greater than two. The initial target market for our memory would be for high speed libraries for government, military and medical archival storage.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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